

**RUSSIAN ACADEMY OF SCIENCES
INSTITUTE OF TERRESTRIAL MAGNETISM, IONOSPHERE AND
RADIOWAVE PROPAGATION**

Preprint of IZMIRAN No 102 (1049)

Lyubimov V.V.

**MAGNETOMETRIC SURVEYS IN THE WEST PART OF THE
BLACK SEA**

**The material of this work was reported during
Indo-Russian Symposium on "Nature and Variations
of the Geomagnetic Field", 2 - 6 February 1993,
New Delhi, India.**

Moscow 1993

РОССИЙСКАЯ АКАДЕМИЯ НАУК
ИНСТИТУТ ЗЕМНОГО МАГНЕТИЗМА, ИОНОСФЕРЫ И
РАСПРОСТРАНЕНИЯ РАДИОВОЛН

Препринт No 102 (1049)

Любимов В.В.

МАГНИТОМЕТРИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ В ЗАПАДНОЙ
ЧАСТИ ЧЕРНОГО МОРЯ

Материалы этой работы были доложены на
индо - российском симпозиуме "Природа
и вариации геомагнитного поля",
2 - 6 февраля 1993 года, Дели, Индия.

Москва 1993

UAK 550.380

Lyubimov V.V. Magnetometric Surveys in the West Part of the Black Sea. Preprint No 102 (1049), Moscow: IZMIRAN, 1993. -26 p.

In the paper adduced the results of magnetometric surveys on board the r/v "Academik" which were carried out by the program of the expedition "EMINE-90".

The results of experimental work by synchronous measurement of geomagnetic field on shipboard and outside the ship are shown here.

It were adduced the maps of the anomalous magnetic field ΔB_T on the magnetic grounds and the map of horizontal gradient G of the measured magnetic field in central part of the magnetic ground No1 which obtained as a result of the expedition.

В работе представлены результаты магнитометрических исследований на борту НИС "Академик", проведенных по программе экспедиции ЕМИНЕ-90. Указаны районы работ.

Приводятся результаты опытно-методических работ по измерению магнитного поля на борту судна. Представлены примеры измерения курсового горизонтального градиента G на отдельных профилях морской магнитной съемки и на полигонах.

Приводятся карты изодинам аномального магнитного поля ΔB_T и курсового горизонтального градиента G , полученные по результатам экспедиции.

ИЗМИРАН, 1993 г.

The marine expedition EMINE-90 on the geologic and geophysic study of the Bulgarian's shelf by the r/v "Academik" was organized by the plan of the scientific and research works of the Institute of Oceanology Bulgarian's Academy of Science. It was carried out in September - October 1990. It was included two stage of the work. The first stage was included only the running methods of the marine researches. The second stage of the expedition was included the work on the station in separately areas and points which were selected by the first stage results of the expedition. Magnetometric surveys were carrying out only in the first stage of the expedition (see Fig.1).

During the expedition was made marine magnetic surveys of the total field force (1150 miles) and its horizontal gradient (830 miles). It was implemented a big volume (440 miles) of an experimental work.

The marine magnetometers of different models: quantum [1, 2], proton [3] and fluxgate magnetometers [4, 5] were used for the magnetic survey. Behind the ship in the different distances from its stern were towed four vehicles with the magnetic sensors. Two magnetic sensors are the proton magnetometer's sensors MBM-1 [3] and PMPM-01 (#) and the two others are sensors of the quantum magnetometer KMB [6]. The sensors of the fluxgate magnetometer FM-2 [4] were placed on board of the ship (see Fig.2 and Fig.3). The results of the measurement were registreted by analog recorders and were calculated by special computers.

During EMINE-90 were obtained the unique experimental results of the synchronous measurement of the ship course

(#) Proton magnetometer PMPM-01 was constructed at the Institute of Oceanology, Varna, Bulgaria.

deviation which was measured on its board and the course deviations of the magnetometer sensors in towed vehicles which were towed in different distances from the ship's stern (see Fig.4). The results of the harmonic analysis of the magnetic sensors course deviation in different distances from the ship's stern are shown in Table too. The result of the data analysis showed a big influence of the ship's body magnetic momentum on the towed magnetic sensors if the distance of towed vehicles from the ship's stern is 3 - 5 times more than its hull's length (see Fig.4 and Fig.5).

More details about the problem of accuracy raising measurement of the horizontal magnetic field gradient by marine towed gradientometer during EMINE-90 are discussed by LYUBIMOV (7, 8).

Magnetic Ground No1.

The ship tracks during marine magnetic survey on the magnetic ground No1 are shown in Fig.6. The sublatitudinal tracks had the ship's course direction $\Phi_k = 75^\circ$ and $\Phi_k = 255^\circ$, and they were assumed the name "F". The submeridional tracks had the ship's course direction $\Phi_k = 150^\circ$ and $\Phi_k = 330^\circ$, and they were assumed the name "R". The other ship's tracks during EMINE-90 were assumed the name "B". 84 tracks of magnetic survey on the area 20 x 27 square miles were made on the magnetic ground No1.

The map of the anomalous magnetic field isodynamas on the magnetic ground No1 is shown in Fig.7.

As a result of the map's analysis it is obviouised that the magnetic field is a very anomalous in central and western part of the magnetic ground. The separate

T a b l e. The harmonic analysis results of the magnetic sensors course deviation in different distances from the ship's stern.

1	On shipboard	$1,69 \cos \psi + 1,02 \sin \psi + 1,83 \cos 2\psi +$ $+ 0,90 \sin 2\psi - 0,11 \cos 3\psi - 0,35 \sin 3\psi -$ $- 0,25 \cos 4\psi$
2	lc = 50 m	$0,39 \cos \psi - 2,66 \sin \psi + 6,16 \cos 2\psi +$ $+ 1,75 \sin 2\psi - 2,09 \cos 3\psi - 2,69 \sin 3\psi +$ $+ 1,61 \cos 4\psi$
3	lc = 100 m	$2,41 \cos \psi + 1,45 \sin \psi + 2,25 \cos 2\psi +$ $+ 0,18 \sin 2\psi - 0,77 \cos 3\psi - 0,92 \sin 3\psi +$ $+ 0,44 \cos 4\psi$
4	lc = 140 m	$- 0,30 \cos \psi + 2,15 \sin \psi + 1,33 \cos 2\psi +$ $+ 0,29 \sin 2\psi - 0,60 \cos 3\psi - 1,04 \sin 3\psi +$ $+ 0,66 \cos 4\psi$
5	lc = 170 m	$- 0,21 \cos \psi + 1,33 \sin \psi + 1,04 \cos 2\psi +$ $+ 0,19 \sin 2\psi - 0,48 \cos 3\psi - 0,99 \sin 3\psi +$ $+ 0,53 \cos 4\psi$
6	lc = 240 m	$+ 0,83 \sin \psi + 0,94 \cos 2\psi +$ $+ 0,16 \sin 2\psi - 0,34 \cos 3\psi - 0,49 \sin 3\psi +$ $+ 0,55 \cos 4\psi$

magnitudes of the anomalies are amount to 1000 nT and more. They have the maximum horizontal gradient of magnetic field from 200 to 1000 nT/km. The magnetic field has a weakly anomalies in the eastern part of the magnetic ground. Its magnitudes exceedn't 100 nT and its horizontal gradient are less than 10 - 20 nT/km.

It is retracing the series of the anomalous structures in west and central part of the magnetic ground which are directing from the north - west to the south - east. Its maximum positive magnetudes are amount to 1000 nT and its negative magnetudes are about 2400 nT on the west and about 1400 nT on the south of the central part of the magnetic ground No1. In central part of the magnetic ground are standed out two positive central anomaly areas with magnetudes 700 and 400 nT. They are stretching in the submeridional direction and are disambered between themselves from the small anomaly area which has a horizontal gradient of the magnetic field about 20 - 50 nT/km (see Fig.8, Fig.9 and Fig.10).

Five profiles of the magnetic survey which have the length about 40 miles in the sublatitudinal direction are shown in Fig.11. The width of the positive anomalous structure, which has the magnetude about 1000 nT, is enlarging from the north - west to the south - east about twice at 4 to 8 km. The width of the negative anomalous structure is only 2 km but its magnetude reach a record value 2400 nT on the magnetic ground No1. Maximum horizontal gradient of the magnetic field which was reached about 4150 nT/km by the sea depth about 45 m was registrated on these tacks of the magnetic survey.

As a result of the gradientometric researches was constructed the map of a horizontal magnetic field gradient for the central part of the magnetic ground (see Fig.12). The maximum value of horizontal gradient of

magnetic field in the central part of the magnetic ground was fixed about 857 nT/km on the profile F34 (see Fig.13).

One of the marine survey tacks which was directed in Burgas's region is shown in Fig.14. It was registered the value of the magnetic field about -62 nT on the measuring base $\Delta l = 20$ m here. It is corresponded to the value of the horizontal magnetic field gradient about -3100 nT/km.

Magnetic Ground No2.

The map of the anomalous magnetic field isodynamics (thick line) and the ship's tracks (dotted line) on the magnetic ground No2 is shown in Fig.15. The maximum depth's over-fall on the magnetic ground No2 is about 32 m by the middle value of the sea depth on it is about 100 m.

The magnetic ground No2 was projected by the system of the sublatitudinal ($\varphi_k = 106^\circ$ and 286°) and submeridional ($\varphi_k = 16^\circ$ and 176°) tacks. The magnetic ground area was consisted 4,5 x 9 square miles and it was covered of the system from the 15-th crossing tacks.

As a result of map's analysis is obviouised that the magnetic field is a small anomalous. It has a linear structure on the magnetic ground No2 with the maximum magnetude ± 30 nT and its the maximum horizontal gradient about 22 nT/km.

Regional Survey (Magnetic Ground No3).

Magnetic survey in the coastal waters of Bulgaria were carried out not only on the magnetic grounds but also on a separately regional tacks which were passed through a certain points of the bore holes C1 - C4 (tacks B5, B8 and B9 in Fig.1). The scheme of the measuring tacks on the magnetic ground No3 with the diagrams of the observed

anomalous magnetic field ΔB_T is shown in Fig.16.

In Fig.17 is shown the map of the anomalous magnetic field isodynamics ΔB_T on the magnetic ground No3. Besides it is shown sea depth in meters here (dotted line).

As a result of the map's analysis it is obvious that the magnetic field in the north - eastward and in the focus of magnetic ground No3 is a weakly anomalies. Its the maximum horizontal gradient value is mount about 10 - 15 nT/km. But the magnetic field B_T has complicated characteristics of the locality in south - west part of magnetic ground No3 (tacks B1, B5, F30 and F33). Maximum value of the horizontal magnetic field gradient was registrated on the tack B5. It was mounted -3150 nT/km on the measuring base $\Delta l = 20$ m.

REFERENCES.

1. Magnetic instruments. Prospect of SKB FP Academy of Sciences USSR. 1978. Troitsk, Moscow Region, 142092, USSR (russ).
2. Lyubimov V.V. and Perfilov V.I. A new quantum magnetometric instruments work out in the Special Design Office of Physical Industry Acad. Sci. USSR. Review // Researches of the cosmic plasma. Moscow. 1980. P. 159 - 170 (russ).
3. Livotov L.L., Nicolaev A.A. and Semevsky R.B. Marine towed magnetometer MBM // Geophysitcheskaja apparatura. Leningrad, "Nedra", 1979. V.69. P. 31 - 40 (russ).
4. Fluxgate magnetometer FM-2. Prospect of Physics Instrumentation Center General Physics Institute Acad. Sci. USSR. (CFP IOFAN). Troitsk, Moscow Region, 142092, USSR.
5. Lyubimov V.V. Compact, efficiency and inexpensive

- component variometers for science and medicine needs.
Preprint of IZMIRAN No60 (1007). 1992. -21 p. (russ).
6. Ivanitsa A.I. and Fastovsky U.V. Quantum differential magnetometer KMB // Geomagnetnoe priboroostroenie. Moscow, "Nauka", 1977. P.16 - 21 (russ).
 7. Lyubimov V.V. About the problem of accuracy raising measurement of the horizontal magnetic field gradient by marine towed gradientometers. Preprint of IZMIRAN No51 (998). 1992. -20 p. (russ).
 8. Lyubimov V.V. Experimental results of a measuring base noise determination of the marine gradientometer. Preprint of IZMIRAN No103 (1050). 1993. -33 p.

Fig. 1. Ship tracks during magnetic survey EMINE-90.
 (ground №1, ground №2, * - points, where make deviation researches of the magnetometer's sensors).

Fig. 2. Scheme of magnetometer's equipment which were placed on board the r/v "Academik".
 (FM-2 -fluxgate magnetometer, KMB -quantum magnetometer, MBM and PMPM -proton magnetometers, S.C. and K -special computers, T.R.-typewriter, A.R. -analog recorder, C -computer).

Fig. 3. Scheme of magnetometer's sensors and other equipment which were towed during marine survey EMINE-90. (1- ship, 2- beams, 3 and 9 -sparkers, 4- sensor of magnetometer PMPM-01, 5 and 6 - sensors of magnetometer KM8, 7 - sensor of magnetometer MBM-1, 8- seismic hydrophones).

Fig. 4. Experimental results of researches the course deviation of the ship (on shipboard) and the magnetometer's sensors in towed vehicles which were towed in different distances from the ship's stern.

Fig. 5. Experimental results of measurement three-components of magnetic field with a three component magnetometer FN-2 on shipboard (B_x , B_y and B_z) and with sensors of marine gradientometer KMS in towed vehicles which had different measured base sl.

Fig. 6. Ship tracks during marine magnetic survey EMIB-90 on the Ground №1.

FIG. 7. The map of anomalous magnetic field AB_T on the ground No. 1. Section of isodimamas is 100 nT. (Negative anomalies are dotted line).

Fig. 8. Itineraria tacks on the ground N81 with the diagrams of total force observed magnetic field B_T . Positive anomalies are black.

Fig. 9. Central part of the ground M-1. Separately itineraries tracks with the diagrams of observed magnetic field.

Fig. 10. Separately itineraries tacks on the ground N01 with the diagrams of observed anomalous magnetic field ΔB_T (R-tacks) and its horizontal gradient G (GR-tacks) on the measurement base $\Delta l = 70m$. Positive anomalies are black.

Fig. 11. Separately itineraries tracks during EMINE-90 with the diagrams of observed anomalous magnetic field ΔB_T . Positive anomalies are black.

Fig. 12. The map of horizontal gradient G of the measured magnetic field in the central part of the Ground No 1. Section of isodines of magnetic field gradient is 10 mT/km . Dotted lines are showed depth of the sea. Section of sea depth is in meters.

Fig. 13. Separately itineraries tracks of the central part of the ground N=1 with the diagrams of observed anomalous magnetic field (ΔB_T) and its horizontal gradient (G). Diagrams of horizontal gradient of the measured magnetic field are black.

Fig. 14.
One of the tracks of marine geomagnetic survey during KALINE-90 to the Burgess region (tack B1) where was registered the maximum value of horizontal gradient of magnetic field-3100 nT/km on the measuring base $\Delta l = 20 \text{ m}$. In the picture are shown diagrams of observed total magnetic field (B_T), its horizontal gradient (G) and sea depth (h).

Fig. 15. The map of isodinance of anomalous magnetic field ΔB_T on the ground K42 observed during EXPL-90. Section of isodinance is 10 mT. Dotted line are shown the ship's tracks.

Fig. 16. Scheme of a measuring tacks on the magnetic ground No 3 with a diagrams of observed anomalous magnetic field ΔB_T . Positive anomalies are black.

Fig. 17. The map of anomalous magnetic field ΔB_T on the magnetic ground No3. Section of isodynamas is 50 nT. Dotted line are shown sea depth in meters.